

BLACK HOLE MASS ESTIMATION FROM LUMINOSITY OF ACTIVE GALACTIC NUCLEI

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ABSTRACT

In this article considered, black hole mass estimation methods from using spectral and photometric observations of active galactic nuclei in the optical range. In addition, here has been proposed a new method for estimating the mass of a black hole using only photometric observations in the optical range.

Key words: black holes, active galactic nuclei, observation

I Introduction. It is necessary to analyze a large amount of observational data to estimate the mass of the black hole in their central part from spectral and photometric observations of active galactic nuclei (AGN) in different bands. Using data from spectral observations, we can estimate black hole masses using various methods, but the method of estimation from photometric observations in the optical range alone has not been considered yet [1, 2]. In the following sections, we first consider how to estimate black hole mass from spectral and photometric observations, and then how to estimate black hole mass from only photometric observations (B,V,R) in optical band. Here we use observational data from several well-studied AGN [1-5]. In order to analyze the methods of black hole mass estimation, we collected data from different sources on different types of active galaxies. In addition, we have obtained additional information about our facilities from <https://simbad.u-strasbg.fr/simbad/sim-fid> an online database of additional

facilities. After analyzing and studying all these, we estimated various parameters of some poorly studied objects through our proposed method.

II Analyzing of black hole mass estimation methods. In this section, we first looked at the methods of estimating the mass of the black hole in their central part based on the observational data of active nuclei galaxies, and then we analyzed the results obtained by which method are closer to the observational data. Considering the methods, we performed some typical calculations and compared them with observational data of well-studied quasars, Seyfert I and Seyfert II type AGN. Our main goal is to show that by analyzing these methods it is possible to estimate the mass of the black hole in their central part only through the quantities obtained from photometric observation in the optical band.

2.1 Black hole mass from stellar velocity dispersion. We can use the Stellar Velocity Dispersion to estimate the black hole mass at the center of nearby galaxies because in nearby galaxies there is apparently a close connection between the central black hole and the bulge kinematics [6]. For example, black hole mass (determined from spatially resolved kinematics) correlates well with stellar velocity dispersion, as $M_{\text{bh}} \propto \sigma^{3.75}$ (Gebhardt et al. 2000a) or $M_{\text{bh}} \propto \sigma^{4.8}$ (Ferrarese & Merritt 2000). In generally

$$M_{\text{BH}} = 10^c \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma}{200 \text{ km/s}} \right)^d \quad [2]$$

Here c and d constant coefficients, their values for low luminosity AGN: $c = 8.13 \pm 0.06$ and $d = 4.02 \pm 0.32$ [6].

2.3 Mass estimation from luminosity. In general case black hole mass estimation from luminosity of AGN as follow:

$$\ln \left(\frac{M_{\text{BH}}}{M_0} \right) = a + b \ln \left(\frac{L(5100\text{\AA})}{10^{44} \text{ erg/s}} \right) + c \ln \left(\frac{\text{FWHM}}{\text{km/s}} \right) \quad [3]$$

Here a, b, c are constant coefficients, FWHM is line width. The values of coefficients a, b, c take different values for different objects, for example, for z3.5 quasars $a = 1.07 \pm 2.62$, $b = 0.48 \pm 0.88$ and $c \approx 2$ [1].

There are many empirical relations similar to the above, and almost all of them depend on spectral observations. Our goal is to try to estimate through

photometric observations the mass of the black hole in the central part of AGN. We use some well studied AGN observational data, as well as observational data from other AGNs using the **Symbad** search engine, to explore how to estimate black hole mass below. In this below (see fig.1 and fig.2) given black hole mass – luminosity and black hole mass - velocity dispersion relations for some well studied AGNs.

Fig.1

Fig.2

III The optimization method for estimation of black hole mass. Figure 1 above shows the relationship between the luminosity of some well-studied AGNs and the logarithmic values of the black hole masses in their central part. As can be seen from the figure, there is a linear regression between the luminosity of some AGNs and the black hole mass (yellow straight line in the figure on the right), and for some there is almost no such relationship (inside the rectangle in the figure on the right those given). In general, the linear regression relationship can be expressed as follows:

$$y = ax + b$$

Here a, b are constant coefficients, and $y = \lg \frac{M_{BH}}{M_0}$; $x = \lg (L/\text{erg} \cdot \text{s}^{-1})$. In our case $a = 0.9 \pm 0.173$, $b = -32,8 \pm 2.332$. From Fig.2 we found $\lg \frac{M_{BH}}{M_0} = c \cdot \sigma^d$ and for our situation $c = 2.359 \pm 0.0047$, $d = 0.23 \pm 0.00034$. It should be noted that our results are based on the observational data of approximately 300 AGNs, and in most cases give more accurate results for SY1 and SY2 type AGNs (i.e. give results close to the results

obtained from spectral observations). For quasars and other objects with large redshifts, this relation cannot be applied.

Discussion and conclusion. So far, the mass of a super-massive black hole estimated by various methods is on the order of $10^8 M_0$ (M_0 is the mass of the Sun). In the theoretical calculations, including the calculation of the energy release through the Penrose mechanism, the maximum value of the mass of the super-massive black hole came out in the order of $10^{10} M_0$. We believe that the results obtained from spectral and photometric observations are closer to the real value. Therefore, when making typical calculations, the mass of a super-massive black hole should be considered to be in the order of from $10^8 M_0$ - $10^{10} M_0$.

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